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INNOVATIONS IN SUSTAINABLE GASTRONOMIC TOURISM: A SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT PERSPECTIVE IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role of local gastronomic sustainability in promoting tourism within globalized, mass-driven trends, focusing on the region of Ohrid in the Republic of Macedonia. It highlights the importance of preserving culinary identity and cultural heritage, while exploring innovations in sustainable food tourism that contribute to the area's socio-economic development. The research emphasizes how these practices enhance the region's appeal as a tourist destination, addressing both the challenges and opportunities posed by globalization. Through a review of literature and critical analysis, the study advocates for collaborative efforts between local stakeholders to advance sustainable gastronomic tourism in Ohrid and the Balkan region. Strategies include integrating traditional food practices with modern sustainability standards, fostering innovation in food production, and enhancing marketing efforts focused on authenticity. These approaches aim to ensure Ohrid's long-term global competitiveness and its role as a key driver of regional socio-economic development.

KEY WORDS: Gastronomic sustainability, culinary identity, sustainable food tourism, globalization, socio-economic development, Ohrid

INTRODUCTION: GLOBALIZATION, LOCALITY AND FOOD TOURISM

While the prevalent globalization imaginary rests on a shift from the local to the global, and indeed many tourism destination choices are determined by the political and economic circumstances of globalization, societies are still oriented around local attachments (Angelichin-Zhura, 2023). In fact, locality is central to identity, “it is how we are placed by others and how we place ourselves” (ibid, p.95). Present in and constitutive of international flow of capitals and mobilities, locality is the fundament of tourism. A destination can only be experienced through physical presence and immediate engagement with its people, nature, culture. One distinctive facet which is connected to the senses, and as such directly and intrinsically linked to cognitive and affective stances is food. Food represents an essential part of both intangible and tangible heritage, it is a crucial marker of people’s identity, tradition, their relationship to nature, construction of place and culture. It is, therefore, a co-structor of meaning when the local and the visitor meet.

Accordingly, one continuously distinguishing factor that influences the development and success of the tourism and hospitality industry within today’s globalized world is gastronomy, and in particular, gastronomic tourism. It is precisely through the art of gastronomy that tourist destinations seek to innovate and distinguish themselves by creating alternative experiences that not only distinguish them from others, but also elevate the entire tourist offer of the locality and region. The strengths of gastronomic tourism are in that it brings together different aspects - the art of cooking, agriculture, natural and cultural heritage and tradition of a tourist destination. And while this is already well-documented in the literature (Scarpato, 2002; Richards, 2002; Gálvez et al., 2017; Vuksanović, 2017), research has moved forward calling for the development of sustainable tourism (Sims, 2009), having identified and elaborated on the negative effects of mass tourism on the environment, cultural heritage and socio-economic issues for local inhabitants. continuously growing research has been published on sustainable tourism, with particular attention to food tourism and innovative food design in respect to the climate, cultural, economic and social conditions (Hall and Gössling 2016, Clansy, 2017; Leer, 2020). These elements include more than just a passive consumption attitude of the visitor, but induce and include respect towards the local environment, the cultural and natural heritage, and local culture – from which the food element is inseparable (Leer, 2020). In a continuously expanding range of travel and experience choices globally, fast-changing and competitive trends that reflect on the success of the tourism

industry, sustainable, educational offers that connect to the affective element will attract visitors with greater buying power, those oriented towards active experiences and enabling for the development of a sustainable visitor influx throughout the year.

This article, hence, offers a review of relevant research on gastronomic tourism and its contribution to a continual, sustainable local socio-economic and cultural development; it further reflects on the Balkan gastronomic identity, focusing on Ohrid, Macedonia through a critical lens; and, through an illustrative case representing an advancement of gastronomic tourism while preserving local traditions, it argues for the strong potential of sustainable gastronomic tourism in the region. Finally, it offers recommendations for future research on sustainable food tourism in Ohrid and the region, and its potential impact on local and regional economic development.

FOOD TOURISM ASPECTS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

In the attempt to conceptualize the relationship between tourism and food, different terms have been used in the literature, such as “food tourism”, “gastronomic tourism”, “culinary tourism”. Without arguing for or against interchangeable use of these terms, we point out to one definition of “food tourism” provided by Ellis et al., who argue that it “is about cultural anthropology through understanding the interactions of tourists with place through the medium of food” (2018, p.261). As Leer adds to his understanding of this definition, food thus represents “a gateway to experiences of authenticity, interpersonal contact and other cultural aspects which might be found in other kinds of cultural tourism” (2020, p.68). He, however, suggests that it would be more useful to understand food tourism as “all practices targeted tourists (national or international) that are centered on some kind of food and/or drink practices – material, cultural, practical or other” (ibid).

While we believe that a distinction between the terms can be useful in more detailed argument developments and studies, we will not be differentiating the terms food tourism and gastronomic tourism. This is because our argument is tied to the *locality* feature of this food-centered tourism niche. Inherently, food tourism relates to multiple aspects: interest in the history, traditions, values and culture of a place through food; curiosity to experience different tastes through ingredients and local ways of preparation of the food; acquiring knowledge about the place through the aforementioned facets. Therefore, and as we pointed out in the introduction, food has always played and continues

to play an even more important role as part of cultural tourism (Richards, 2002; Vuksanović, 2017). In that regard, we find it useful to differentiate between the “gastronomic identity” and the “gastronomic image” of a tourist destination. An already established gastronomic identity supports tourism which connects with the local production, preparation, promotion of the offer, and acquainting the visitor with the foods and their use. The gastronomic image is created after the introduction to the visitor – it refers to the outside perception about the local products and the food offered (Cañizares & Guzman, 2012).

Gastronomic identity is intrinsically linked to heritage, an aspect that we will briefly touch upon further below. Research clearly shows how food has become a crucial part of the perceived attractiveness of a tourist destination (Loi et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2021; Huete-Alcocer & Hernández-Rojas, 2022) which ties both gastronomic identity and gastronomic image. Additionally, when it comes to World Heritage places - as is the case of Ohrid - which already have outstanding universal value from both natural and cultural perspective, an established image and its promotion are deeply linked to cognitive and affective images – beliefs about and perceptions of the place, as well as emotional response to both tangible and intangible characteristics (Baloglu & McCleary, 1999; Beerli & Martin, 2004; Smith et al., 2015). For example, studies from Spain (Andalusia), Italy (Sicily) and Romania (Sibiu) have shown that not only tourists interested in local gastronomy spend more money in the destinations, but that the compelling combination of cultural heritage, natural beauty and local cuisine can be a successful marketing strategy for regional tourism development (Cañizares and Guzmán, 2012; Gálvez et al., 2017; Privitera et al, 2018). Additionally, research has shown that apart from the benefits for the local economy, gastronomic tourism can benefit regional development (Hall and Gössling, 2016). Parallely, various countries have already applied a broad political focus on food tourism to sustain new economies, social networks and cultural initiatives in rural areas with increased depopulation due to urbanization, centralization and the disruption of traditional agriculture and industry in these areas (Slocum and Curtis, 2017).

The notable existence of travelers whose primary tourist interest is gastronomic is not only visible through thematic tours offered in many popular tourist destinations such as wine-tasting, wine-pairing, cooking classes, “pick your food and cook it”, “catch and cook your lobster” etc., but also through the increasing demand for even more differentiating experiences (Privitera et al. 2018). These include a more immediate relationship between the visitor

and the local – agritourism, eating locally grown and organic products are just a few aspects. Noticeable is the appeal of an affective educational experience – the story that the traditional dish has to tell, with its deep cultural mark. This brings us back to the established fact of the close link between the success of a tourist destination and its gastronomic identity and image (Belisle, 1983). In relation to this, the specific methods of food preparation are an important precondition for attracting tourists to a destination. In an increased competitive climate for such offers particularly under the influence of social media, new models are sought after in order for visitors to retain a positive image of a product or a place, return and subsequently recommend the destination to others (Loi et al., 2017; Prayag et al., 2017). The above-discussed appeal is documented by research showing that the customer’s/visitor’s needs are connected to the human aspect of production, additionally to cultural (traditional preparation, values), historical (traditional preparation) and environmental resources (Oosterveer, 2006; Smith and Xiao, 2008; Marks, 2011). What is also becoming increasingly important is the fusion of global trends and concepts with local applications, which tourists find recognizable and unique enough at the same time. This seems to be the future for developing and growing the tourism sector sustainably, but also strengthening the local socio-economic circumstances.

BALKAN GASTRONOMIC IDENTITY AND IMAGE DEVELOPMENT POTENTIAL

As Vuković and Terzić (2020, p.2) elaborate in their study, gastronomy has continuously been the “most positive aspect” in relation to the image of tourism in the Balkan region, making it a significant part of the branding and promotion of Balkan tourist destinations. Along others, they point out to the tourists’ preferences for traditional food and preparation methods (*ibid*), viewed as a cultural symbol of the place (Vuksanović, 2017).

Relying on historical reflections informed by Jovan Cvijić (1918, 1922), Vuković and Terzić (2020) attempt to tackle the perceived distinction between “traditional local food” and “regional food” in the Balkans. What can be inferred from their attempt, is in fact the prevalence of shared history, migration flows and cultural exchange in the region that has resulted in a richness of variants of preparation of food, vast expression of identity and values through food and variations of ingredients used. While intentions to protect culinary authenticity and diversity can be useful in some instances (UNESCO’s nominations to world intangible heritage and the EU’s quality

place-based labeling), some, such as *halloumi* cheese and *Turkish delight*, have become highly contested, adding fuel to already existing ethnic, national, and political conflicts (Welz, 2013). Scholars point out to the danger of codification and diminishment of the variety of versions, and the role of different places, people, and sociohistorical circumstances that have contributed to dish creation, as well as contemporary “living practices” (Bortolotto, 2013, p.65).

In this context, having what we see as an advantage of recognizability as “Balkan food” as a typical culinary experience (Vuksanović et al., 2019), we propose focusing on initiatives such as the course of eco gastronomy and joint food-design efforts (Goodman et al., 2012; Leer, 2020). The region has much to offer also with regards to specific cultural meanings (Vuksanović, 2017), and as part of local, national, and regionally shared intangible cultural heritage: it involves knowledge passed from generation to generation, rituals and customs to foraging, harvesting, fishing and hunting, continuing with seasonal food, preparation, preservation of food and all the way to consumption and its connection to custom and tradition. The potential is enormous for creating competitive gain and adding sustainable value to the entire Balkan region, tourism, agriculture, entrepreneurship and repopulation of areas – by which Macedonia and other Balkan countries are strongly affected. Vuković and Terzić recognize this potential and propose for countries in the region to work together towards building a “unique joint Balkan gastronomy tourism experience” (2020, p.20).

OHRID’S GASTRONOMIC IDENTITY

Ohrid’s culinary heritage is deeply rooted in local traditions, primarily driven by the natural beauty of Lake Ohrid and its agricultural traditions. Traditional dishes like grilled trout, herb-baked fish, and vegetable stews celebrate local and seasonal ingredients. However, this rich culinary identity has been fading, as most restaurants in Ohrid cater to tourist demands for fast food and generic, internationally recognizable dishes. As a result, authentic local cuisine rarely appears on menus, with many restaurants failing to maintain quality, particularly during the busy summer season relying heavily on inexperienced staff.

The local gastronomic sector, thus, faces several challenges, including inconsistent quality and a lack of focus on traditional dishes. According to previous research by one of this article’s authors, most of the top

internationally known dishes in Macedonia are being improvised and have gone out of their original state – one such example being the pastry delicacy *eclair* (Naumov et al., 2022). This can be attributed to the impossibility of obtaining a certain type of goods, prices and local living standard, but also the misconception of certain food specialties. While observing that Ohrid as a culinary destination has perhaps passed the opportunity to offer food which is known world-wide, Naumov argues that Macedonia should adhere to its native cuisine and refrain from offering global dishes if its people cannot correctly identify eclairs (ibid).

However, these challenges that Ohrid and the country are facing also present opportunities: Embracing *locavorism*—prioritizing local, seasonal ingredients—could revive Ohrid’s culinary identity, offering tourists a unique dining experience based on the area’s natural resources. Incorporating elements of "rooted globalization", where local chefs reinterpret global dishes with local ingredients, could also be a strategy for revitalizing Ohrid’s food scene. This, in turn, would start (re)building its gastronomic image as well.

SUSTAINABLE FOOD TOURISM PERSPECTIVES: AN ILLUSTRATIVE CASE

The proposed opportunities do reflect existing efforts: A prime example of sustainable agritourism and the potential for locavorism in Ohrid is the Pirustija Nedanoski rural household, a family-run business since 2005 in the village of Ramne. The household offers authentic rural accommodation combined with a traditional gastronomic immersive experience. Two rooms are available for rent, styled in traditional Macedonian decor. Guests are encouraged to book early, especially during the summer season when visitor numbers increase. This household embodies the garden-to-table concept, where visitors can experience the full food creation process, from picking fresh ingredients to enjoying a traditionally home-cooked meal made from zero-mile food.

The village of Ramne is situated on the slopes of Petrino Mountain within the boundaries of Galicica National Park, at an altitude of 960 meters above sea level. The location has a moderate continental climate, greatly influenced by a large quantity of water from the nearby mountain springs. The village is under direct Sub-Mediterranean influence approaching from the south-west. This terrain is very suitable for growing a different variety of vegetables and fruits. The village is also well known for its tasty potatoes. All these favorable

conditions make the location attractive and suitable for the household's gastronomic tourism offer.

Pirustija Nedanoski offers traditional Macedonian dishes such as “koshmispite”, “komat”, “presnec”, “pitulici”, “gjomelze”, “Ohrid pretzels”, “bofci”, “bread in a pot”, “chomlek”, game meat “sarmi”, stuffed peppers, moussaka, various roasts, salads, homemade “rakija” (brandy), homemade wine and homemade jams and marmalades, prepared using family recipes and locally grown produce. Their focus is on traditional pastry with seasonal vegetables, fruits, and locally sourced dairy and meat, which provides visitors with an authentic taste of Ohrid's gastronomic traditions. The entire concept of working with groups of visitors is to provide guests with a full day immersed in the countryside. They are not passive order-takers or mere consumers of food; instead, they are active participants who can engage in the entire process. Visitors are welcomed with homemade sweets from the orchard and pure, tested cold spring water. The preparation and production unfold right before their eyes—from grinding the flour, chopping vegetables, collecting eggs from the henhouses, kneading the dough, and rolling it out, to finally witnessing the baking process.

By providing this immersive food experience, the household offers an alternative to the more commercialized dining options available in the city and its surroundings, showing that agritourism can be a powerful tool in shaping the future of Ohrid's gastronomy. In this regard, the Nedanoski family plays a key role in preserving and promoting Ohrid's rural food heritage. Their example not only highlights the importance of local food production but also underscores the potential of sustainable rural tourism in revitalizing Ohrid's culinary identity. There are similar cases of agritourism in the country, through which rising competition encourages securing a stable culinary tourism development.

While we believe that the revival of traditional food preparation is central to the sustainable development of Ohrid's gastronomic tourism and the preservation of Macedonian cultural identity in a globalized world, we are aware that flexibility is key in keeping up with the innovative trends around the world. As highlighted in the previous section, one strategy could also entail local reinterpretation of global dishes. One such example is illustrated in a study on innovative sustainable food experience in the Faroe Islands (Leer, 2020). Informed by the New Nordic Cuisine movement, which conceptualizes preparing the food only with ingredients that naturally grow in the region (Leer, 2016) and arguing for a “re-design” of the experience (ibid, 2020, p.66),

with the visitors' active participation in the center (also Calzati and de Silvo, 2017), the study brings additional attention the flexibility aspect. Namely, the case presented involves different sets of activities which include foraging, preparing the food together, doing physical work activities – all of which include and promote the *locality* aspect – but the dish prepared with freshly picked local nettles is globally known one – pizza (Leer 2020, p.75). According to the author, this allows for “accessibility” when it comes to the taste palette – a familiar food choice is offered, while retaining traditionally used, locally grown herbs in the region (ibid, p.77f).

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDED APPROACHES

Gastronomic tourism is a continuously expanding form of cultural tourism that seeks to satisfy the demand of a market segment related to food experiences. Because of the social and cultural contact that is fostered, as well as the financial benefit, gastronomic tourism has grown significantly as a phenomenon and is now one of the most innovative and dynamic areas of the travel industry. The local community in a tourist destination benefits in many ways from gastronomic tourism. For instance, it raises standards of living, generates employment opportunities, encourages the preservation of cultural traditions, the environment, and natural resources, and promotes the spread and consumption of local cuisine. As the research we reviewed from different regions shows, not only does gastronomic tourism increase the quality of visitor experience, but it also enables sustainable growth. Based on this, it can be argued that sustainable gastronomic tourism as an urgent point for consideration, will improve local economic growth, will strengthen the resilience of the local community, will help preserve biodiversity and cultural heritage, and induce social change towards tourist interaction, overall helping Ohrid to uphold and improve its position as an attractive tourist destination. In this article, we have argued about the potential of local and traditional food, while remaining flexible to innovations which require balanced openness. Sustainability remains the biggest challenge in the region in the sense of merchandise provision and obtaining substantial quality in the placement of local food. Continuing to develop sustainable gastronomic tourism options will address these issues which range from declining biodiversity to rural and city depopulation and stalled economic development. In this sense, we maintain that traditional food is Ohrid's and Macedonia's comparative advantage in the competition of gastronomic tourism destinations as it is connected to the rich cultural and natural heritage and economic development potential.

In the lack of comprehensive research and policy development on sustainable and innovative food tourism in Macedonia, we recommend a few research approaches to begin with: In collaboration with state agencies, local government and tourist agencies, the profile of the culinary tourist in Ohrid and in Macedonia needs to be researched, while keeping continuous comprehensive track of the evolution of general tourist flows. Here, an advantage enabled by social media should be used to perform online ethnographic research of visitors' posts, blogs and reviews about Ohrid and the region with regards to food experiences. This will help gain better understanding of the affinities and perceptions of tourists in creating a targeted gastronomic tourism approach. Furthermore, thorough research needs to be done that identifies the diversity and quality of the offer of local ingredients for their potential in the recognizability of the gastronomic identity and image. These attempts, we argue, can be useful to understand the pathway of local products, and with that, sustainable, eco-gastronomy, to become prevalent for visitors' perceptions and affective relationship development. Moreover, conducting participatory collaborative research with farmers, chefs, and businesses such as the family-run service illustrated in this article will help gain an understanding of the maintenance of the supply chain and of the creation of existing traditional dishes as well as innovative preparations, their view on market potential, and of their challenges. Finally, collaborative research that covers the Balkan region needs to be performed to examine the relationship between culinary heritage and gastronomic openness of the region to better understand the challenges and opportunities for cooperation and mutual offer as a gastronomic tourism destination.

Findings from such studies will serve as key information for innovative planning, tourist offers and policy development that promote local gastronomy and preservation of heritage, while increasing tourism visibility and attractiveness. Only through a holistic synthesis of these features can a way be paved for gastronomic tourism to become a successful distinctive marker based on a sustainable compromise between the local and the global.

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